

EXPERIMENTS ON THE SYNTHESIS OF FURANO COMPOUNDS. PART IX.
A SYNTHESIS OF α -BRAZAN AND THE RELATED QUINONE*

BY J. N. CHATTERJEA

Syntheses of α -brazan and the related *o*-quinone (isolated as the quinoxalin derivative, VII) are reported. Cyclisation of γ -3-dibenzofurylbutyric acid furnished the cyclic ketone (XI) which was converted into β -brazan and its 10-methyl derivative.

In a previous communication an unambiguous synthesis of α -brazan (I: R=H) from 4-dibenzofuryl-lithium was described (Chatterjea, this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 369). A general route to the same ring system is now described starting from 2-phenylcoumarone-3-carboxylic acid (II).

A synthesis of the acid (II) from *o*-hydroxyphenylacetonitrile was reported in a previous paper (this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 175). This has now been prepared in a better overall yield from the keto-nitrile (IV), obtained by the condensation of ethyl benzoate and *o*-methoxyphenylacetonitrile. On treatment with alcoholic hydrogen chloride in the presence of calculated amount of water, this nitrile (IV) afforded a mixture of the corresponding ester (V) along with a small quantity of the related amide (cf. Wislicenus *et al.*, *Annalen*, 1924, 486, 88). The ester (V) underwent demethylation, cyclisation and hydrolysis on boiling with aluminium chloride in benzene, affording the acid (II) along with *o*-hydroxybenzylphenyl ketone (VI, isolated as the oxime).

* A preliminary account appeared in *Exper.*, 1956, 12, 18.

This was followed by homologation by the Arndt-Eistert procedure to 2-phenylcoumarone-3 acetic acid (III), isolated by way of the amide. This acid underwent cyclisation in quantitative yield with phosphoric anhydride in boiling benzene, yielding 5-hydroxy- α -brazan (I:R = OH). On oxidation with chromic acid, this α -naphthol derivative, furnished a mixture of products from which the quinoxalin derivative (VII) was isolated on condensation with *o*-phenylenediamine. The structure of this compound, originally prepared by Kruber and Oberkobusch (*Chem. Ber.*, 1951, 84, 831) from α -brazan, is established by the present synthesis. On oxidation with hydrogen peroxide this hydroxybrazan afforded the dicarboxylic acid (VIII) which was identified by decarboxylation with lime to 2-phenylcoumarone. Reduction by boiling hydriodic acid furnished α -brazan in good yield.

The syntheses of 2-methyl-5-hydroxy- α -brazan and of the corresponding quinone were carried out in a similar manner.

A different synthesis of α -brazan was projected from γ -3-dibenzofurylbutyric acid (IX) which was expected to furnish on cyclisation the ketones (X) and (XI): Actually, however, (X) was never obtained, the sole product being (XI) on cyclisation with H_2SO_4 .

In this connection, it may be recalled that two ketones were derived from γ -2-dibenzofurylbutyric acid (this *Journal*, 1953, 30, 103) and that on the application of Skraup's method to 3-aminodibenzofuran, two isomers were obtained in nearly equal amounts, the ring-closure having taken place in both possible directions (Mosettig and Robinson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 57, 902). The butyric acid (IX) was obtained from 3-nitrodibenzofuran in the following sequence:

The structure of the ketone (XI) has been determined by converting it into β -brazan, structure of which is now well established. 10-Methyl- β -brazan was prepared from (XI) by the usual method.

E X P E R I M E N T A L *

o-Methoxybenzyl Cyanide.—This was prepared from *o*-methoxybenzaldehyde via the azlactone after Baker *et al.* (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 1860) with two minor useful changes, viz., (i) the azlactone was hydrolysed with boiling alkali for a longer period (1½ hours) and (ii) the bisulphite compound of *o*-methoxyphenylpyruvic acid

* All m.ps. are uncorrected.

was decomposed with strong HCl for 2 hours with constant stirring on a boiling water-bath. The overall yield of the cyanide was 46-48%, m.p. 69.5°.

Keto-nitrile (IV).—A mixture of the above cyanide (1.5 g.) and freshly distilled ethyl benzoate (1.5 g.) in benzene (15 c.c.) was added to dry sodium ethoxide (from Na, 0.23 g.) and refluxed on the water-bath for 4 hours. The mixture was treated with iced water, unchanged material removed with ether and the aqueous layer acidified to furnish an oil (1.1 g.) which solidified on keeping. Crystallised from acetic acid the nitrile was obtained in colorless prisms, m.p. 88-89°. (Found: C, 76.6; H, 5.2; N, 5.6. $C_{16}H_{13}O_2N$ requires C, 76.5; H, 5.2; N, 5.6 per cent). The *anil*, obtained by boiling the keto-nitrile with aniline, crystallised from alcohol in colorless plates, m.p. 162°.

If the above condensation is done with powdered potassium in benzene, an equally good yield of the keto-nitrile is obtained and an alkali-insoluble byproduct, m.p. 289° (colorless plates from acetic acid), is also formed in small quantity. (Found: N, 6.4 per cent).

Ethyl (o-Methoxyphenyl)-benzoylacetate (V).—The foregoing keto-nitrile (5.6 g.) was added to a mixture of dry alcohol (30 c.c.) and water (0.8 c.c.) and then saturated with dry HCl gas in the cold and left at the ordinary temperature for 48 hours. Alcohol was then removed by distillation when ammonium chloride separated from the solution. The mixture was poured into water and extracted with ether. The residue on removal of ether afforded the *amide* (IV:CONH₂ in place of CN; 1.3 g.) which crystallised from alcohol in colorless needles, m.p. 155°. (Found: N, 5.1. $C_{16}H_{13}O_2N$ requires N, 5.2 per cent). The mother-liquor on keeping deposited colorless lumps of the ester (V) (4.0 g.), crystallising from alcohol in colorless prisms, m.p. 71-72°. (Found: C, 72.3, 72.3; H, 5.4, 5.7. $C_{18}H_{15}O_4$ requires C, 72.5; H, 6.0 per cent).

2-Phenylcoumarone-3-carboxylic Acid.—The above ester (2.0 g.) was dissolved in dry benzene (20 c.c.); treated with anhydrous AlCl₃ (4.2 g.) and refluxed on the water-bath for 2 hours. On cooling two layers separated. The mixture was decomposed with ice, extracted with ether, dried, filtered from slimy matter and then the solvent removed. The residue was treated with warm 15% NaOH solution (30 c.c.) and filtered hot. The filtrate deposited fine colorless plates of the *sodium salt* of the acid (II) (0.6 g.) (filtrate A) which was acidified to furnish the acid, crystallising from alcohol in colorless needles, m.p. and mixed m.p. 195° (Found: C, 75.3; H, 4.2. Calc. for $C_{15}H_{10}O_3$: C, 75.6; H, 4.2 per cent). The identity was further confirmed by converting the acid into the *amide*, m.p. 261°, undepressed on admixture with an authentic specimen (Chatterjea, *loc. cit.*).

The alkaline filtrate (A) was treated with hydroxylamine hydrochloride (1 g.) and heated on the water-bath for 4 hours. On acidification, the *oxime* of *o*-hydroxybenzylphenyl ketone, m.p. 138-39° (from alcohol), was obtained. Dilthey and Quint (J. prakt. Chem., 1931, 131, 1) report m.p. 138-39° for the oxime. (Found: N, 6.2. Calc. for $C_{14}H_{10}O_2N$: N, 6.1 per cent). If the filtrate (A) is carefully acidified in the cold, a mixture of the *o*-hydroxybenzylphenyl ketone (unstable) and 2-phenylcoumarone (derived from the ketone by facile cyclisation); m.p. 105-119°, is obtained.

The m.p. was raised to 120° either on keeping or by short treatment with warm acid, and the material was fully identified as 2-phenylcoumarone by mixed m.p., colour reaction and by analysis. (Found: C, 86.5; H, 5.3. Calc. for $C_{14}H_{10}O$: C, 85.6; H, 5.2 per cent). Dilthey and Quint (*loc. cit.*) and Yates (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 5376) also record the cyclodehydration of the ketone in the process of isolation.

2-*m-Tolylcoumarone-3-carboxylic acid* was prepared from *o*-hydroxyphenyl-acetonitrile. A mixture of the nitrile (2.8 g.), ethyl *m*-methylbenzoate (3.4 g.) in pure dry benzene (25 c.c.) was added to anhydrous sodium ethoxide (from Na, 1.0 g.) and refluxed for 18 hours. The cooled mixture was treated with iced water, the alkaline layer acidified and the product isolated with ether. After removal of the ether, the residue was dissolved in acetic acid (6 c.c.), treated with HCl (conc., 1 c.c.) and warmed on the water-bath for 2 hours. The whole mixture was basified when 3-cyano-2-*m-tolylcoumarone* (2.1 g.) separated, crystallising from acetic acid in colorless plates, m.p. 71-72°. (Found: N, 6.1. $C_{16}H_{11}ON$ requires N, 6.0 per cent). With sulphuric acid the compound slowly developed a pinkish colour.

On hydrolysis with alcoholic sodium hydroxide on the water-bath for 8 hours, this cyano compound afforded the corresponding *amide* (quantitative yield), crystallising from acetic acid in colorless needles, m.p. 241°. (Found: N, 5.7. $C_{16}H_{13}O_2N$ requires N, 5.6 per cent). On further hydrolysis in diethyleneglycol (10 c.c.) with NaOH (0.6 g.) at 200° for 14 hours, this amide (0.25 g.) furnished a mixture of acids which on crystallisation from dilute alcohol afforded 2-*m-tolylcoumarone-3-carboxylic acid* (0.11 g.), m.p. 168-69°. (Found: C, 76.5; H, 5.0. $C_{16}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 76.2; H, 4.8 per cent). *m*-Toluic acid was obtained from the alcoholic mother-liquor.

2-*Phenylcoumarone-3-acetic Acid*.—2-Phenylcoumarone-3-carboxylic acid (2.0 g.) was converted into the acid chloride by boiling with purified thionyl chloride (4 c.c.) in dry benzene (10 c.c.) and a drop of pyridine. The volatile distillable materials were removed in vacuum, last traces being removed by the addition of benzene (2 × 5 c.c.), followed by its removal in vacuum. The oily acid chloride was dissolved in dry ether (20 c.c.), filtered from pyridine hydrochloride and added dropwise with stirring to a cooled solution of diazomethane (from nitrosomethylurea, 6 g.) in ether (70 c.c.). The mixture was left overnight in the cold when crystalline diazoketone separated. After removal of ether in vacuum, the *diazoketone* was collected and obtained from benzene-petroleum ether in yellowish prisms (1.8 g.), m.p. 126-27° (decomp.). (Found: N, 10.1. $C_{16}H_{10}O_2N_2$ requires N, 10.7 per cent). A solution of the diazoketone (1.7 g.) in pure dioxan (40 c.c.) was added slowly to a solution of silver nitrate (2.0 g.) in NH_4OH (conc., 12 c.c.) at 65°-70°. After the addition, the mixture was maintained at 70° for 1½ hours and at 100° for 1 hour. The mixture was filtered, diluted with water, the precipitated *amide* collected and hydrolysed with aqueous alcoholic potash (12%) for 4½ hours. The alkaline solution was diluted with water (30 c.c.), clarified by norite, filtered and acidified to provide the *acetic acid* (III), which crystallised from ethyl acetate-light petroleum in colorless plates, m.p. 142-43°, yield 1.4 g. (Found: C, 76.4; H, 5.1. $C_{16}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 76.2; H, 4.8 per cent). With H_2SO_4 the compound developed a yellow colour which turned

green and then orange-red. The *p*-toluidide, prepared by way of the acid chloride, crystallised from acetic acid in colorless leaflets, m.p. 209° (Found: C, 80.7; H, 5.6. $C_{23}H_{19}O_2N$ requires C, 80.9; H, 5.6 per cent).

2-m-Tolylcoumarone-3-acetic acid was prepared from *2-m*-tolylcoumarone-3-carboxylic acid in the same way as above through the related *diazoketone*, and obtained in yellow needles, m.p. 126-27° (decomp.). The acid crystallised from ethyl acetate-light petroleum in colorless fluffy needles, m.p. 114°, yield 70%. It developed with H_2SO_4 a yellow colour, turning green to orange-red. (Found: C, 76.4; H, 5.2. $C_{17}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 76.6; H, 5.3 per cent). The *p*-toluidide crystallised from acetic acid in colorless plates, m.p. 190°. (Found: N, 4.7. $C_{24}H_{21}O_2N$ requires N, 3.9 per cent).

*5-Hydroxy-2-braza*n.—The acid (III, 1.2 g.) was dissolved in warm dry benzene (40 c.c.) and treated with phosphoric anhydride (7 g.) and refluxed on the water-bath for 3½ hours. The mixture was treated carefully with ice, the benzene layer washed with sodium carbonate solution, dried and the solvent removed. The residue (0.9 g.) of nearly pure *5-hydroxy-2-braza*n was collected, washed with alcohol and crystallised from acetic acid in cream-coloured crystalline mass, m.p. 204-205°. (Found: C, 82.1; H, 4.5. $C_{16}H_{10}O_2$ requires C, 82.1; H, 4.3 per cent). The compound is almost insoluble in alcohol and difficultly soluble in aqueous alkali.

*2-Methyl-5-hydroxy-2-braza*n was similarly prepared from *2-m*-tolylcoumarone-3-acetic acid and obtained in cream-coloured plates, m.p. 165-66° from acetic acid. (Found: C, 82.5; H, 4.9. $C_{17}H_{12}O_2$ requires C, 82.3; H, 4.8 per cent). Attempt to prepare the methyl ether with methyl iodide and potassium carbonate in acetone gave unchanged material.

Oxidation of *5-Hydroxy-2-braza*n

(a). *With Chromic Acid*.—To a boiling solution of the phenol (0.4 g.) in purified acetic acid (20 c.c.) was added a solution of chromic acid (0.5 g.) in water (0.5 c.c.). A vigorous exothermic reaction took place; boiling was continued for ½ hour, most of the acetic acid removed by distillation in vacuum and then the solution diluted with water. The precipitated orange-red resinous material was collected, washed, dissolved in acetic acid (5 c.c.) and heated with *o*-phenylenediamine (0.1 g.) for a few minutes, when the *quinoxalin* (VII) separated as a yellow crystalline material (100 mg.) which on crystallisation from alcohol was obtained in greenish yellow needles (filtrate shows green fluorescence), m.p. 250-53° (Kruber and Oberkobusch, *loc. cit.*, report m.p. 252-53°). (Found: C, 83.0; H, 4.1. Calc. for $C_{22}H_{12}ON_2$: C, 82.5; H, 3.8 per cent). The *quinoxalin*, derived by condensation with *o*-toluylenediamine, was obtained from acetic acid in greenish yellow needles, m.p. 241° (with prolonged sintering). (Found: N, 8.5. $C_{23}H_{14}ON_2$ requires N, 8.4 per cent).

*2-Methyl-5-hydroxy-2-braza*n on similar oxidation with chromic acid provided the corresponding *o*-quinone, characterised as the *quinoxalin* derivative, m.p. 252° from acetic acid. (Found: N, 8.2. $C_{23}H_{14}ON_2$ requires N, 8.4 per cent).

(b). *With Hydrogen Peroxide*.—A suspension of the phenol (0.2 g.) in boiling acetic acid (4 c.c.) was treated gradually with hydrogen peroxide (4 c.c., 30%). The

mixture became slightly reddish, and boiling continued for $1\frac{1}{2}$ hours when all the material went into solution. On precipitation with water 2-(*o*-carboxyphenyl)-coumarone-3-carboxylic acid (VIII) was obtained. This was purified by clarifying the alkaline solution with norite. The acid was obtained from dilute alcohol as a colorless mass, m.p. $279-80^\circ$. (Kruber and Oberkobusch, *loc. cit.*, report m.p. $280-81^\circ$). On decarboxylation with the aid of lime, 2-phenylcoumarone, m.p. 120° , was obtained.

α -Brazan.—A mixture of 5-hydroxy- α -brazan (0.1 g.) and HI (*d* 1.7, 4 c.c.) was boiled under reflux for 6 hours. α -Brazan condensed on the inner wall of the condenser as colorless, long, prismatic needles, having the characteristic odour. The whole mixture was extracted with ether, washed with sodium thiosulphate, filtered, dried and the solvent removed. The residual oil, which slowly solidified, was crystallised from alcohol in long prismatic needles, m.p. and mixed m.p. $102-103^\circ$ (Kruber and Oberkobusch, *loc. cit.*, report m.p. $103-104^\circ$).

Infra-red spectrum: (Fig. 1). $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{nujol}}$: 8.31s, 8.48s, 9.49s, 11.49s, 12.13s, 13.25s; 9.15m, 10.91m, 12.71m; 6.35w, 6.56w, 7.13w, 7.45w, 7.64w, 7.83w, 8.22w, 8.64w, 12.33w and 14.66 μ .

FIG. 1

3-Aminodibenzofuran.—3-Nitrodibenzofuran (1.0 g.), prepared according to Borsche and Bothe (*Ber.*, 1908, **41**, 1940), was suspended in alcohol (15 c.c.) and shaken in an atmosphere of hydrogen in the presence of Raney nickel (5 c.c. sediment) for $1\frac{1}{2}$ hours when approximately 3.2 molecular proportion of hydrogen was absorbed and the suspended material went into solution. On concentration after the removal of the catalyst, the amine was obtained in a pure condition on careful addition of water. This was obtained in colorless plates (0.9 g.), m.p. 94° . Borsche and Bothe report m.p. 94° .

3-Cyanodibenzofuran was prepared from the foregoing amine by Sandmayer's reaction according to Borsche and Bothe (*loc. cit.*). The best yield of the purified material (m.p. $122-23^\circ$; lit., m.p. 120°) was 25%; use of sodium cyanide in place of potassium cyanide gave inferior results (yield 16-20%). The nitrile is best purified by crystallisation from acetic acid.

3-Acetyldibenzofuran.—A solution of the above cyanide (12.0 g.) in benzene (35 c.c.) was added to an excess of methylmagnesium iodide (*ca.* 2 moles) in ether.

The mixture was refluxed for 2 hours and then left overnight. Next day, the complex was decomposed with ice and HCl, the organic layer separated, washed with water and the solvent removed under reduced pressure. The residue was crystallised from alcohol in colorless plates (7 g.), m.p. 144°. (Found: C, 80.0; H, 5.0. $C_{14}H_{10}O_2$ requires C, 80.0; H, 4.8 per cent). The 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone crystallised from acetic acid in orange-red needles, m.p. 282-83°. (Found: N, 13.7. $C_{20}H_{14}O_8N_4$ requires N, 14.3 per cent).

3-Bromoacetyldibenzofuran.—A solution of the foregoing methylketone in chloroform (20 parts) was treated at the room temperature with bromine (1 mole). Towards the end of the addition, the evolution of hydrogen bromide was copious. After removal of the solvent, the bromoacetyl compound was obtained in quantitative yield, crystallising from acetic acid in colorless plates, m.p. 150-52°. (Found: C, 57.7; H, 2.7. $C_{14}H_9O_2Br$ requires C, 58.1; H, 3.1 per cent).

β-3-Dibenzofuroylpropionic Acid.—A solution of the foregoing bromoketone (3.2 g.) in benzene (12 c.c.) was added to a suspension of sodiummalonic ester (sodium, 0.25 g., ethyl malonate 1.8 g.) in benzene (25 c.c.). The mixture was refluxed for 3 hours. Sodium bromide separated quickly. The mixture was acidified, the benzene layer separated and the solvent removed in vacuum. The crystalline residue was refluxed for 1 hour with MeOH-KOH (2 g. in 30 c.c., 50%). The potassium salt of the malonic acid separated towards the end. Methanol was removed by evaporation and the residue extracted with hot water (charcoal), filtered and acidified. The crude malonic acid (3.5 g.) was dried and heated at 190°-200° (oil-bath) for 10 minutes when the evolution of carbon dioxide was substantially complete. The dark melt was extracted with sodium carbonate solution, clarified with charcoal and acidified. Brownish crystals of the propionic acid (1.5 g.) were obtained, crystallising from acetic acid in brownish plates, m.p. 210-12°. (Found: C, 72.0; H, 4.8. $C_{14}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 71.7; H, 4.5 per cent).

γ-3-Dibenzofurylbutyric Acid.—The above keto-acid (1.0 g.) in diethyleneglycol (5 c.c.) containing KOH (0.8 g.) was treated with hydrazine hydrate (0.8 c.c., 90%) and refluxed mildly for 1½ hours. After removing water by distillation, the temperature was raised to 205° and maintained at this temperature for 3 hours. The mixture was diluted with water, acidified with HCl (conc.) and the butyric acid (0.9 g.) crystallised from benzene-light petroleum in colorless plates, m.p. 116°. (Found: C, 76.0; H, 5.5. $C_{16}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 75.6; H, 5.5 per cent).

10-Keto-7:8:9:10-tetrahydro-β-brazan.—The above butyric acid (0.6 g.) was dissolved in 90% H_2SO_4 (20 g.) and the dark mixture left at the ordinary temperature for 20 minutes and then poured into ice. The crystalline product was collected, washed with dilute NaOH solution and crystallised from alcohol. The ketone was obtained in long homogeneous leaflets (0.16 g.), m.p. 131°. A further yield (0.04 g.) of the same product (m.p. and mixed m.p. 131°) was obtained from the mother-liquor. (Found: C, 81.0; H, 5.3. $C_{14}H_{12}O_2$ requires C, 81.4; H, 5.1 per cent). The oxime crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 217-18°. (Found: N, 6.2. $C_{14}H_{12}O_2N$ requires N, 5.6 per cent).

β-Brazan.—A slurry of LiAlH_4 (0.1 g.) was added to a solution of the above cyclic ketone (0.05 g.) in ether (10 c.c.) at the ordinary temperature with the exclusion of moisture. The reaction mixture was decomposed after 20 minutes with ethyl acetate and then acidified with HCl (dil.). The ethereal layer was dried (sodium sulphate), the solvent removed and the residual gum mixed with palladised charcoal (15 mg.) (Linstead and Thomas, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 1127) and heated at $310^\circ\text{--}320^\circ$ for 2 hours. The whole mass was then repeatedly extracted with warm benzene which on concentration furnished beautiful plates of *β-brazan*, m.p. and mixed m.p. $206\text{--}207^\circ$; yield 30 mg.

10-Methyl-β-brazan.—A solution of the above ketone (0.09 g.) in anhydrous ether (5 c.c.) was added to an excess of ethereal methylmagnesium iodide, and the mixture refluxed for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. After decomposing with ice and HCl , the carbinol was isolated as a viscous gum which was dehydrogenated with palladised charcoal (100 mg.) for 2 hours at $300^\circ\text{--}320^\circ$. *10-Methyl-β-brazan* was obtained in colorless plates (25 mg.), m.p. $90\text{--}92^\circ$ from a small volume of ethanol. (Found: C, 88.4; H, 5.6. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}$ requires C, 87.9; H, 5.2 per cent).

The author wishes to thank Principal M. Q. Daja and Prof. B. P. Gyani for facilities. The absorption spectrum was kindly taken by T. Mukherjee of Wayne University.

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
SCIENCE COLLEGE, PATNA-5.

Received November 19, 1955.